

Does it fit? The impact of scene context on temporal and spatial characteristics of the object manipulation in a pick-and-place task

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Purpose

In daily life, we are often confronted with a combination of a visual search task and subsequent object manipulation. Most studies investigating interaction with objects, such as grasping and moving objects between different locations, focused on isolated items (e.g. [1]). Yet, we daily interact with numerous objects placed in a rich environment. Previous research showed that visual search could be affected by the scene context (e.g. [2]). Here, we extend the potential impact of scene context to interactive phases in a pick-and-place task.

Q: In a pick-and-place task, does the scene context primarily impact only the searching behaviour? Or is the object's manipulation (reach, transport) also affected?

Methods

Experimental approach

- Psychophysics study in VR
- 13 naïve participants
- 3 conditions: congruent, incongruent, empty

- 3 VR scenes (office, kitchen, bathroom), 2 variations for each
- 21 target objects – anchor pairs
- 10 distractors per scene

Example of one trial: task phases

Analysis

- Hand and head movement, eye-tracking data
- Linear mixed effect model analysis (R, nlme library)

- Task, search, reach, transport duration
- Scene coverage
- Proportion of gaze on object and anchor
- Anchor-object transition

Results

Discussion

- Performance improvement (shorter task duration) in congruent condition was primarily caused by facilitated search which is indicated by shorter search time
- Likewise, indicated by scene coverage, participants had to gaze around more when the object did not match the context
- Interestingly, search time was not different between congruent and empty conditions
- In context-poor “empty” environment, search seems to be mostly based on physical attributes of the target
- Once placed in context-rich scene, but when the contextual information is non-informative, the larger number of visual stimuli served as a distractor
- When the contextual information was relevant, it compensated for the large number of visual stimuli and maintained the search time comparable to the “empty” scenario
- No effect on reach phase. Only a small effect on transport phase presumably caused by more obstacles in context-rich scenes
- Participants spent less time and effort to find target object in congruent condition resulting in proportionally more gazing on object
- Anchor was gazed on more when it was relevant for the task performing
- Target object was not always fixated after the anchor. Nonetheless, shorter anchor-object transition in congruent condition underlines the role of anchor

Conclusion

The study evaluated the scene context impact on the performance of a pick-and-place task. The interactive phases (reach, transport) appear to be rather unaffected (Q). This strengthens the validity of transferring eye and hand movement knowledge in an isolated setting to a realistic context-rich scenario.

References

- [1] Lavoie, E. B., Valevicius, A. M., Boser, Q. A., Kovic, O., Vette, A. H., Pilarski, P. M., Hebert, J. S., & Chapman, C. S. (2018). Using synchronized eye and motion tracking to determine high-precision eye-movement patterns during objectinteraction tasks. *Journal of Vision*, 18(6), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1167/18.6.18>
- [2] Vö, M. L. H. (2021). The meaning and structure of scenes. *Vision Research*, 181, 10–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2020.11.003>